

DURABILITY OF CARBON/CERAMIC COMPOSITES SUBJECTED TO ELECTRICAL LOAD

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1 Introduction

The rapidly developing field of materials science requires new multifunctional materials that can work as high temperature heating resistors and in reactive and changing atmospheres. Carbon-carbon (C/C) composites are candidates for high-temperature applications due to their appropriate values of thermal and electrical properties. Moreover, C/C composites are light, retain their high strength and stiffness at high temperatures (up to 2000 °C), and, due to a low coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) and a high heat of sublimation, they have good ablation resistance [1,2]. The main disadvantage of carbon-based materials is their low oxidation resistance. For this reason, ceramic materials characterized by good oxidation resistance have been progressively incorporated in carbon-based materials to protect them against the environment [1-3].

Maximum temperature and watt loading are the most important parameters characterizing heating resistors. Watt loading is defined as the electrical power per unit area dissipated by a heating element, and it is limited at high voltages by electrical breakdown of the material. Together with the maximum temperature of the intended application, they are the main limiting factors for the design of heating elements. The resistor temperature depends on how much energy has to be transmitted from the heating element to the surrounding area, and it depends as well as on the temperature of this area. On the other hand, with respect to the watt loading capability, it is clear that a higher value of this parameter is generally an advantage for the use of such material as heating element. Reduced values

of watt loading capability generally make necessary the use of larger heating elements, and therefore produce an increase of costs.

The practical limits of watt loading for the most often used heating resistors that can work in oxidative atmosphere are as follows: 8 to 12 W/cm² for metallic elements, 10 to 15 W/cm² for silicon carbide, and 20 to 30 W/cm² for molybdenum disilicide. The disadvantage of metallic elements is that the resistance of resistors made with these elements increases with time because of reduction in cross-section by oxidation and elongation, leading to eventual failure. The drawback of silicon carbide and molybdenum disilicide elements is that they are made of ceramic material, so they are brittle [5]. Metallic, silicon carbide, and molybdenum disilicide heating resistors can produce 1400 °C, 1650 °C and 1850 °C maximum temperature in air atmosphere, respectively. Carbon/carbon composites are not brittle, present watt loading above 80 W/cm² and maximum working temperature up to 3000 °C, however they can work only in nonoxidative atmospheres.

Carbon/carbon/ceramic (C/C/ceramic) composites reinforced with carbon fibers are potential candidates for structures working at elevated temperatures, as well as high temperature heating elements. Similarly to C/C composites, they retain high strength and modulus at high temperature, however, due to the presence of a ceramic phase they have a distinctly higher oxidation resistance. Moreover, their fracture toughness is higher than for silicon carbide and molybdenum disilicide.

The aim of this work is to investigate electrical properties and heating efficiency of C/C

composites impregnated with polysiloxane preceram as well as their durability in their working conditions. They should retain their mechanical parameters at high temperature, and additionally they should provide high durability. Using the preceram is a new low cost and very promising way to obtain carbon-ceramic composites and to protect them against oxidation [3,4].

2 Material fabrication.

The C/C composites were manufactured by the liquid impregnation procedure. Two types of carbon roving, differing in mechanical properties, were used (see Table 1). Carbon roving was wrapped onto a rotating cylindrical drum in order to form a kind of tape. The carbon fiber tape was then impregnated with Novolac MR phenol-formaldehyde resin (ZCH Organika – Sarzyna, Poland) or with a mixture of the resin with UF15 SiC powder (SiC_p from H. C. Starck, type StarCeram S, grains P 50 %, diameter = 0.55 μm). After drying, the impregnated fiber material was removed from the drum, cut into the desired shape and laid up (stacked) in a metallic mold in the required orientation (1D). This composite preform was then isostatically pressed and cured. In the next step, samples were heat treated in an inert argon atmosphere at the temperature of 1000 °C (see Table 2 for a summary of the types of C/C samples prepared in this way). The C/C composites obtained in this step were then cut into bars, whose dimensions were approximately 3 mm x 5 mm x 80 mm, and impregnated with Lukosil 901 polymethylphenylsiloxane preceram (produced by Lucebni zavody, Kolin, Czech Republic), mixed with the previously mentioned SiC_p, and subjected to heat treatments at 1000 °C and at 1700 °C in an inert atmosphere. This procedure allowed for obtaining C/C/ceramic composites. As a result of the heat treatment with the impregnated polysiloxane preceram, samples which were heat treated at 1000 °C contain silicon oxycarbide in their matrices, while samples that were heat treated at 1700 °C contain silicon carbide in their matrices. The different types of prepared C/C/ceramic samples are summarized in Table 3. The C/C composites used as a comparison reference for the C/C/ceramic composites obtained at 1700 °C were also treated at this temperature in

order to establish a valid comparison. For the C/C/ceramic composites obtained at 1000 °C, there was no need to perform a similar treatment to the reference C/C composites, since they have already undergone a similar treatment in the last step of their fabrication.

3 Material characterization.

Electrical measurements were conducted in a quartz tube in an inert atmosphere (argon). Samples with the form of bars were contacted with graphite grips, achieving a good electrical contact. Increasingly high electrical currents (from 10 A to 90 A) were then passed through the samples, using a variable electrical transformer. The flow of these high currents produced a heating effect on the samples, until the maximum value of current was achieved or failure of the sample occurred. The temperature as well as current – voltage relationships were registered. The temperature changes of the composites, accompanying the changes of the electrical parameters, were monitored by means of an optical pyrometer in the range from 800 °C to 2500 °C.

The resistance of the composite samples was calculated from the Ohm's law. The quantity of dissipated electrical power on composite samples (watt loading) was calculated from the formula:

$$P_s = P/S \quad (1)$$

where P is the electrical power (W), S is the composite surface (cm²), and P_s is the watt loading (W/cm²) [5].

In order to estimate the durability of the composites, samples were subjected to non-destructive ultrasonic measurements before electrical tests and after the tests. The ultrasonic wave velocity in all composites was measured in the laminates direction. After that, the Young's modulus in this direction was calculated. Mass losses of composite samples after electrical tests were also estimated.

4 Results

4.1 Electrical measurements

As mentioned in the previous experimental section, the electrical resistance of the samples was registered as the current and temperature of the

sample increased, starting from 800 °C. In Figure 1 we show a comparison of the resistance at 800 °C between the C/C/ceramic and the C/C reference samples treated at 1000 °C (which means that the ceramic phase is silicon oxycarbide). The first observation that becomes apparent from this figure is that the C/C/SiCO composites possess a distinctly higher electrical resistance than their C/C references. If we increase the current through the samples until the temperature of 1400 °C is reached, the results of Figure 2 are obtained, in which we see that the difference in electrical resistance between the two types of samples has decreased, due to a generalized decrease of resistance at this temperature, but still the C/C/SiCO composites present higher values of electrical resistance than their C/C counterparts in all cases analyzed. The general decrease of resistance at 1400 °C, compared to the values at 800 °C, is in agreement with the expected negative temperature coefficient (NTC) behaviour of the electrical resistivity of these samples, since the predominant effect that determines the values of resistivity as a function of temperature is the carrier generation.

If we now turn our attention to the samples prepared at 1700 °C, i.e. samples in which the ceramic phase is SiC instead of SiCO, then quite different results are observed. In Figure 3 we see the electrical resistance of these samples when the current passing through them is producing a heating effect that increases the temperature to 800 °C. As it can be observed from the error bars, any significant differences in the values of electrical resistance between the C/C/ceramic composites and their C/C reference samples have disappeared. Within the margins of the error bars, both C/C/ceramic and C/C composites have the same values of resistance. If we increase the current so that the temperature of the samples increases up to 1400 °C, then the results of Figure 4 are obtained. Again, a general reduction of electrical resistance is observed compared to the values at 800 °C, but the differences between C/C/ceramics and their C/C references continue to be not significant.

4.2 Watt loading and maximum temperature

We have calculated the watt loadings of the investigated composites at the maximum temperature reached during the heating process, which corresponds to the maximum current

circulating through the sample before electrical breakdown was observed. The results for the samples with a SiCO ceramic phase (treated at 1000 °C during the fabrication process) are presented in Figure 5 and they are compared with their C/C composite counterparts (without ceramic phase). In general, the maximum watt loading achieved is smaller for the composites with a SiCO ceramic phase, compared to those that only have a carbon matrix (except for some samples fabricated with UTS fibers, in which no significant differences were detected). These results should be analyzed in connection with the resistance measurements, in which samples with a SiCO phase systematically showed higher resistances (Figs. 1 and 2). Higher resistances mean lower currents for the same applied voltages, so the lower watt loading obtained for these samples is a consistent result. In the case of the UTS fibers, it was observed in Fig. 2 that the differences in electrical resistance for the samples made with them were less significant in the high temperature (i.e., high current) measurement range, so the less significant differences in watt loading values are also an expected result.

If we do an analogous comparison for the C/C/ceramic composites treated at 1700 °C during the fabrication process, i.e. the samples in which the ceramic phase is SiC instead of SiCO, we observe the results shown in Figure 6. In this case, no significant differences are observed between the C/C/SiC composites and their C/C reference samples. This is in agreement with the results of Figures 3 and 4, in which we observed no significant differences in electrical resistance between these samples. Since the values of electrical resistance were similar for samples with or without the ceramic (SiC) phase, then it is expected that the watt loading effects will also be similar, as we have just demonstrated. Hence, we can summarize by saying that densification and heat treatment of the composites in these conditions do not have influence on their watt loading: C/C/ceramic composites obtained at 1700 °C withstand the same watt loading as their reference C/C composites.

Figures 7 and 8 present the maximum temperature that was generated from the heating resistors before electrical breakdown occurred. All C/C/ceramic composites heat treated at 1000 °C (with a SiCO ceramic phase) achieve lower

maximum temperatures than their C/C references, regardless of the type of fiber used. In general, these results agree with the lower values of watt loading achieved for the samples with SiCO ceramic phases (Fig. 5), because lower currents are expected to cause weaker heating effects. In the case of the C/C/ceramic composites heat treated at 1700 °C (with a SiC ceramic phase), we can observe in Fig. 8 two different behaviours. On the one hand, when UTS fibers are used, no significant differences are observed between the maximum temperature achieved with resistor samples that contain the SiC ceramic phase and those that only have a carbon matrix. This is in agreement with the similar values of maximum watt loading that are observed for this type of samples in Fig. 6. But, on the other hand, when STS fibers are used as starting material, a significant increase of the maximum attainable temperature is observed for the C/C/SiC composites compared to the reference C/C composites. This is not connected with differences in watt loading, since for these samples no significant differences are observed in Fig. 6. Therefore, we have to conclude that, for these particular samples, a similar watt loading and electrical resistance between the C/C/SiC ceramics and their C/C counterparts does not mean similar heating effects. Since the values of electrical resistance and watt loading are similar, the circulating electrical currents will also be similar, but the heating effects are stronger for the samples containing the SiC ceramic phase only when STS fibers are employed. This behaviour cannot be attributed only to the STS fibers, because in the case of a SiCO ceramic phase there is a decrease of the maximum attainable temperature for the densified samples with respect to those with only carbon matrix, for both types of fibers. Hence, the only possible explanation must be in the interaction between the STS fibers and the SiC matrix in terms of heating efficiency, but at this moment this behaviour is not completely understood (a tentative explanation will be given in next section).

The values of maximum watt loading for C/C/ceramic composites presented in Figs. 5 and 6 are distinctly higher in comparison with conventional heating resistors. In general, it is possible to observe in Figs 5 to 8 that the highest watt loadings and highest temperatures are achieved

for C/C/ceramic composites heat treated at 1700 °C, i.e. with a SiC ceramic phase (Figures 6 and 8).

4.3 Young modulus

In figures 9-12 we show the values of Young's modulus for our samples before and after electrical measurements. In the case of the samples heat treated at 1000 °C, i.e. with a SiCO ceramic phase, we can observe that the values of Young modulus are always higher for the densified samples (samples with ceramic phase) compared to those with only carbon matrix (Fig. 9). After the electrical tests (Fig. 10), the samples experiment a generalized and very significant decrease of the Young modulus, except for some samples like DSa and Ua, that we attribute to not reaching a full electrical breakdown in these cases.

For the samples treated at 1700 °C (SiC ceramic phase), there are no significant differences in Young modulus between samples with or without the ceramic phase (Fig. 11). The same behaviour was observed for these samples when we compared the electrical resistance (Figs. 3 and 4) and watt loading (Fig. 6). The values of Young modulus for these samples are significantly lower than for the samples treated at 1000 °C (Fig. 9), both for the C/C composites and for the C/C/SiC composites. It is clear that the temperature has an important influence on this parameter. After the electrical tests, the samples with only carbon matrix experiment a very significant decrease of Young modulus (Fig. 12), but the C/C/SiC composites maintain their values of Young modulus almost unaltered. Hence, it can be concluded that C/C/SiC samples are durable while subjected to electrical load and they do not exhibit changes of Young's modulus.

Finally, table 4 contains data for mass losses of all samples after electrical tests. In the case of samples with only carbon matrix (Sa, Sb, Ua, and Ub) no mass losses were detected. The same can be said about the densified samples (with a ceramic matrix phase) subjected to heat treatments at 1700 °C, i.e. when the ceramic phase is SiC. However, when the ceramic phase is SiCO instead of SiC, i.e. when the heat treatment is at 1000 °C instead of 1700 °C, there are mass losses detected after the electrical breakdown, and they are more significant for the samples fabricated with STS fibers than those with UTS fibers. The mass losses of the samples

with SiCO ceramic phase are attributed to loss of oxygen produced by the heating effects during the electrical tests. The significant differences of mass losses between samples with STS and UTS fibers is worth to analyze, specially taking into account that a different behaviour was also observed between samples containing these two types of fibers in connection with the maximum attainable temperature for C/C/SiC composites (Fig. 8). UTS fibers have higher strength and similar Young modulus than STS fibers. This means that UTS fibers have undergone additional high temperature processing steps during their fabrication, which can make them more immune to chemical reactions with the C/ceramic matrix. These chemical reactions can be at the origin of the higher loss masses that C/C/SiCO composites with STS fibers experiment during the electrical tests (that increase the temperature at more than 1500 °C). They can also explain why samples with STS fibers, after being subjected to the 1700 °C temperature treatment that originates the C/SiC matrix, are capable of reaching higher temperatures during the electrical tests than their UTS counterparts (Fig. 8).

Summarizing, the main conclusion of Table 4 is that C/C/ceramic samples obtained at 1700 °C (with a SiC ceramic phase) are more durable than those obtained at 1000 °C (with SiCO ceramic phase) while being subjected to electrical load, because they do not experience any mass loss in contrast with the significant mass losses (and even visible damage) of the SiCO samples.

5 Conclusions

Carbon-ceramic composites obtained at 1700 °C (with a SiC matrix phase) can be used as heating elements with watt loading up to about 90 W/cm². They do not experience any significant mass losses and their Young modulus stays unaltered after applying such watt loadings. In comparison, C/C composites experience a significant decrease of their Young modulus after application of watt loading. In the case of carbon/ceramic composites obtained at 1000 °C the ceramic matrix phase is made of SiCO instead of SiC and their durability after watt loading is significantly inferior: they experience noticeable mass losses and a substantial decrease of their Young modulus. Additionally, the values of watt loading and maximum achievable temperatures are

generally higher for the samples with a SiC phase compared to those with a SiCO ceramic matrix.

Hence, it is concluded that C/C/ceramic composites heat treated at 1700 °C are good candidates for application as heating elements, although their industrial introduction still requires further investigation on long term reliability, under thermal shock and in oxygen-containing atmosphere conditions.

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Figure 1. Resistance at 800 °C of C/C and C/C/ceramic (SiCO) composites heat treated at 1000 °C

Figure 3. Resistance at 800 °C of C/C and C/C/ceramic (SiC) composites heat treated at 1700 °C

Figure 2. Resistance at 1400 °C of C/C and C/C/ceramic (SiCO) composites heat treated at 1000 °C

Figure 4. Resistance at 1400 °C of C/C and C/C/ceramic (SiC) composites heat treated at 1700 °C

Figure 5. Watt loading of C/C and C/C/ceramic (SiCO) composites heat treated at 1000 °C

Figure 7. Maximum temperature of C/C and C/C/ceramic (SiCO) composites heat treated at 1000 °C

Figure 6. Watt loading of C/C and C/C/ceramic (SiC) composites heat treated at 1700 °C

Figure 8. Maximum temperature of C/C and C/C/ceramic (SiC) composites heat treated at 1700 °C

Figure 9. C/C and C/C/ceramic (SiCO) samples heat treated at 1000 °C - Young's modulus before electrical tests

Figure 11. C/C and C/C/ceramic (SiC) samples heat treated at 1700 °C - Young's modulus before electrical tests

Figure 10. C/C and C/C/ceramic (SiCO) samples heat treated at 1000 °C - Young's modulus after electrical tests

Figure 12. C/C and C/C/ceramic (SiC) samples heat treated at 1700 °C - Young's modulus after electrical tests

Table 1. Types of carbon fibers used as reinforcement

Carbon fibers	Strength [MPa]	Young's modulus [GPa]
STS 563124k, 1600 Tex	4000	240
UTS 50 F13 12k, 800 Tex	4900	240

Table 2. Types of reference C/C composites

Labelling	Carbon fibers	Matrix
Sa	Roving STS 5631	C
Sb	Roving STS 5631	C, SiC _p
Ua	Roving UTS 50 F13	C
Ub	Roving UTS 50 F13	C, SiC _p

Table 3. Types of C/C/ceramic composites

Labelling and names of densified C/C sample	Matrix of composites	
	1000 °C	1700 °C
DSa (densified Sa)	C, SiC _p , SiCO	C, SiC _p , SiC
DSb (densified Sb)	C, SiC _p , SiCO	C, SiC _p , SiC
DUa (densified Ua)	C, SiC _p , SiCO	C, SiC _p , SiC
DUb (densified Ub)	C, SiC _p , SiCO	C, SiC _p , SiC

Table 4. Mass losses of C/C and C/C/ceramic composites after electrical tests

Sample	Mass losses [wt %]	
	1000°C	1700°C
Sa	0	0
Sb	0	0
Ua	0	0
Ub	0	0
DSa	8	0
DSb	16	0
DUa	4	0
DUb	3	0